

Octahedral Complexes of Nickel(II) *Bis* Ethylacetoacetate with Aromatic Heterocyclic Amines

A. Syamal

The preparation and characterisation of hexa-coordinated complexes of cobalt (II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate with aromatic heterocyclic amines had already been described¹. This communication describes the adduct formation of nickel(II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate with aromatic heterocyclic nitrogenous bases like pyridine, 3-methylpyridine, 4-methylpyridine and 3, 4-dimethylpyridine.

General method of synthesis of the adducts: $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.012M) was dissolved in minimum amount of water. Ethylacetoacetate (0.04M) and the requisite heterocyclic base (1 ml.) were added to this. pH of the mixture was adjusted to 6 by addition of dilute ammonia. The pale blue precipitates formed were filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol containing a small amount of heterocyclic base. These were dried in air.

From the method of preparation it is evident that nickel (II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate is formed *in situ* and addition of ammonia favours the pH for the formation of hexa-coordinated adducts. When 2-methylpyridine is used as the nitrogenous base, addition of ammonia results in the formation of green nickel(II) *bis* ethylacetoacetate chelate instead of the six-coordinated 2-methylpyridine adduct. This inability to form adducts might be ascribed to the possible steric hindrance by the 2-methyl group in 2-methylpyridine. All these complexes lose the heterocyclic base on being heated and are less stable than the corresponding acetoacetylarnide² and acetylacetonate³ complexes. When left in air for some days, the complexes slowly liberate the heterocyclic bases and assume a dull colour. Attempts to prepare adducts containing bidentate chelating amines like ortho-phenanthroline and 2-2'-dipyridyl were unsuccessful.

The electrolytic conductance measurements of these complexes were performed in methanol and low molar conductance values ($\Lambda_M = 12-16$ mhos) indicated the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The stereochemistry of nickel (II) complexes is of much current interest both from spectrochemical and magnetochemical point of view. Octahedral nickel (II) complexes generally exhibit four absorption bands around 330, 540, 820 and 950 m μ due to the transitions $3T_{1g} (P) \leftarrow 3A_{1g} (\nu_1)$, $3T_{1g} (F) \leftarrow 3A_{1g} (\nu_2)$, $1E_g \leftarrow 3A_{1g} (\nu_3)$ and $3T_{1g} \leftarrow 3A_{1g} (\nu_4)$ respectively⁴⁻⁵. These bands may be shifted to higher wavelengths with weaker ligand fields⁶⁻⁷. The electronic absorption spectra of these complexes were recorded in mixed alcohols (methanol, ethanol, 1:1) in presence of the respective heterocyclic base in the region of 320-1000 m μ with the help of Hilger Watts Uvispek Spectrophotometer. Three

1. A. Syamal, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press)
2. A. Syamal and R. L. Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, (in press)
3. J. P. Fackler, Jr., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 24.
4. W. Manch and C. Ferocius, *J. Chem. Ed.*, 1961, 38, 192.
5. C. J. Balhausen, *Den. Mat-fys. Medd.*, 1954, 29, No. 4; G. Narnin, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1966, 39, 2298; this *Journal*, 1966, 43, 443.
6. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", (Interscience Publishers Inc., New York), 1962, 735-738.
7. R. S. Drago, *et al.*, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 124.

ligand field bands in the vicinity of 330, 630 and 930 $m\mu$ have been observed with the suggestion of another band beyond 1000 $m\mu$. A thorough survey of the spectra of octahedral nickel (II) complexes with a large number of weak and strong field ligands have led to a generalisation^{4,8} that the $\nu_3:\nu_1$ ratio ranges from 1.6 to 1.8. This range has allowed us an assessment of the position of the fourth absorption band in these adducts. Assuming the 630 $m\mu$ band as the ν_3 band in these complexes, the above taken provides the 1000-1100 $m\mu$ region for the ν_1 band, the existence of which is indicated in the spectra showing an upward trend beyond 950 $m\mu$. On the basis of molar extinction coefficients distinction can be made between tetrahedral nickel(II) and octahedral nickel(II) complexes. Tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes generally show molar extinction coefficient of the order 10^4 , while the octahedral nickel(II) complexes give a much lower value^{7,9}. The molar absorbance of the complexes reported in this study are quite low in comparison to other tetrahedral nickel (II) complexes⁷.

Magnetic moment has often been used as a tool to distinguish between tetrahedral and octahedral nickel(II) compounds. The magnetic moments of tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes are higher than the spin value only due to large orbital contribution arising out of orbitally degenerate ground states. A magnetic moment ranging between 3.5-4.2 B.M. is associated with tetrahedral nickel(II) complexes and a moment 2.83-3.4 B.M. with octahedral nickel(II) compounds.^{6,10,11} The magnetic moments of these complexes were determined by Gouy method at room temperature and the observed values ($\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.9-3.1$ B.M. stand for octahedral nickel(II) complexes.

TABLE I

Analysis, Colour, Molar conductance, Magnetic susceptibility and Electronic absorption spectra of the Complexes

Compound	Analysis		Colour	Molar conductance (30°C) mhos	Spectral data		(B.M.)
	Found %	Reqd. %			λ $m\mu$	Molar extinction coefficient 303° K. litre, mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	
[Co (Py) ₂ (cacac) ₂]	Ni, 12.2 N, 5.6	12.4 5.8	Pale blue	16	330	100*	3.07
					630	6.7	
					930-sh	3.7	
[Co (β -Pic) ₂ (cacac) ₂]	Ni, 11.5 N, 5.5	11.7 5.5	Pale blue needles	15	940	100*	2.96
					330	6.8	
					630	3.6	
					930-sh		
[Co (γ -Pic) ₂ (cacac) ₂]	Ni, 11.5 N, 5.7	11.7 5.5	Pale blue	12	330	102*	3.10
					630	6.5	
					920-sh	3.6	
					930		
[Co(Dime Py) ₂ (cacac) ₂]	Ni, 11.0 N, 5.4	11.1 5.2	Pale blue	16	330	120*	3.12
					630	6.8	
					930-sh	3.5	
					940		

where Py=pyridine, β -Pic=3-methylpyridine, γ -Pic=4-methylpyridine, Dime Py=3,4-dimethylpyridine and cacac=ethylacetoacetate, sh=shoulder.

*High molar extinction coefficient value is due mainly to ligand.

8. M. R. Rosenthal and R. S. Drago, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 840.

9. S. H. H. Chaston *et al.*, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1966, 19, 1401.

10. J. R. Miller, cited in "Advances in Inorganic and Radiochemistry" edited by H. J. Emelius and A. G. Sharpe (Academic Press Inc., New York), Vol. IV, 1962, 147.

11. N. S. Gill and R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3997.

The formula of the complexes $[Ni(\text{amine})_6]^{2+}$, their paramagnetism and electronic absorption spectra suggest that these compounds have an octahedral configuration.

The author wishes to thank Dr. R. L. Dutta for keen interest and constant encouragement. Thanks are also due to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta, Head of the Dept. of Chemistry for extending laboratory facilities and to Mr. A. Mitra for a gift of 3,4-dimethylpyridine.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
BURDWAN, WEST BENGAL.

Received, July 24, 1967.